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Modulation of the formyl peptide receptor in human senescence.

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Certain select systems that possess inhibitory or regulatory function are essential components of the senescence program, like the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR). These components are unique in that they also modulate processes that consider self non-self recognition. We report here discovery of the formyl peptide receptor (FPR1) as an essential component of the senescence program. Function of FPR1 in senescence was supported by co-regulation study which revealed functional association with BATF2, BTLA and TIGIT.